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Who Do You Strive To Be? Exploring Norms of Good Farming for Sustainable Soil Management in Four European Regions

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ABSTRACT

A widespread use of climate-smart soil management practices is needed to meet the challenges posed to farming by climate change. However, it is individual farmers who choose to use such practices or not. Their choices depend on many different factors such as social norms, policy incentives, economic factors, or environmental and local requirements. Understanding norms can thus provide valuable insights into farmers' (potential) use of climate smart soil management practices. In this study, the 'good farmer' concept serves to investigate the norms that farmers hold with respect to their profession. To do so, we use a qualitative research approach and analyse the content of semi-structured interviews with farmers in four case study regions located in Austria, Switzerland, Spain and Sweden. Analysing the views of farmers from different climatic zones in Europe is, to the best of our knowledge, unique. We first identify and describe the characteristics and symbols that are used to define a 'good farmer' and then compare them across contexts. The most frequently mentioned characteristics and symbols across regions are open-mindedness and a willingness to learn, attentiveness and adaptiveness to soil and weather conditions, and being able to time work well, but also having neat and tidy farms and fields. These results are relatively congruent across the case study regions. Economic aspects of farming—for example, being a good businessperson that acts in an economically strategic way—are mentioned in all regions but emphasised especially in the Spanish case study region. We conclude that farmers hold several norms that likely benefit the use of climate-smart soil management practices, such as openness to change, attentiveness and long-term orientation. Other norms are either ambivalent (e.g., norms related to farm economics and business management) or might present barriers (e.g., the importance given to tidy fields) for their uptake. Therefore, we recommend policy incentives which address these norms, such as open mindedness and adaptiveness, rather than focusing primarily on economic incentives. We draw policy recommendations such as revising policy measures to incorporate such norms. For example, we advocate for the establishment and continuation of farmers' networks to foster peer-to-peer learning within communities.

1 | Introduction

Climate change poses great challenges for European farmers. Since agriculture is highly dependent on weather and therefore the climate, maintaining healthy, resilient soils

and farming systems is becoming increasingly important (European Commission 2024). Soil health is influenced by natural factors, as well as farmers' management strategies and practices. Consequently, farmers must adapt their production systems to address these challenges. Management practices

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Highlights

- The ‘good farmer’ concept serves to explore the social norms driving the adoption of sustainable soil practices.
- We analysed 101 interviews to compare farmers’ norms in four European case study regions.
- Some norms of a ‘good farmer’ are shared; others differ across the case study regions.
- Some prevailing norms likely support the uptake; others are neutral or hinder adoption.

such as crop rotations, cover cropping, organic amendments, residue incorporation, and reduced tillage are of importance for adapting to climate change and increased extreme weather events (Droste et al. 2020; Marini et al. 2020; Renard and Tilman 2019). While some of those measures are straightforward to understand, accept, and implement, and thus established in practice, others are less commonly applied (Heller et al. 2024). This is because farms are complex systems, and there is no universal solution that fits all contexts. Addressing one issue within a farm system can create challenges elsewhere (Leeuwis 2004). Implementing new practices involves (economic) risks for farmers since there is often a time-lag between investment and potential payoffs (Sutherland and Darnhofer 2012). As a result, farmers may not implement desired climate-smart practices on all—or even part—of their land.

Understanding the motives behind farmers’ decisions is therefore of significant interest to research. Numerous studies investigate why and when farmers change their practices to achieve benefits related to environmental issues (e.g., Bartkowski and Bartke 2018; Prokopy et al. 2019; Dessart et al. 2019; Klebl et al. 2024; Pronti et al. 2025). They consistently show that the use of such strategies and practices depends, among other things, on behavioural factors, including the norms that farmers hold (Bartkowski and Bartke 2018; Dessart et al. 2019; Ranjan et al. 2019). Norms influence farmers’ decisions through self-identity and the anticipation of the opinion of peers (Westerink et al. 2021). They are sometimes differentiated into injunctive (what farmers believe that others expect from them) and descriptive (observed behaviour of the reference group that is interpreted as ‘normal’ behaviour) norms (Dessart et al. 2019). Norms can serve as entry points for engaging farmers to change their practices (Topp et al. 2024). As they are shaped by the specific social context (Klebl et al. 2024), norms vary across space (and time). Therefore, designing tailored policies and interventions that align with the needs of farmers in different contexts requires a better understanding of farmers’ norms and their variation.

The good farmer (GF) concept offers an approach to study the norms that farmers hold (Burton et al. 2021). The concept posits that farmers carry out actions that lead to them being perceived as a ‘good farmer’ by others in the farming community, thereby increasing their social status. It is well established in rural sociology and is used to understand how the farming

community values and respects different farming practices (Cusworth 2020).

Our study—of explorative nature—thus aims to describe prevailing perceptions of a GF and compare these perceptions between regions. We do so by describing *characteristics* and *symbols* that farmers in four different case study regions hold, interpreting them as the prevailing norms.

This paper addresses the following research questions, using a largely qualitative, interview-based research approach:

- How do farmers in four European regions describe symbols and characteristics of a GF?
- How do these descriptions differ between the selected case study regions?

We then use the GF concept as an interpretative lens to discuss whether these perceptions of a GF may enable or inhibit the use of climate-smart soil management.

The GF concept offers a critical lens for analysing the dynamics and norms of agricultural change. Instead of asking ‘how can we change farmers?’ it focuses on understanding the cultural shifts within farming communities. This view recognises that farmer’s decisions are deeply shaped by the symbols (aspects of farming visible to others, e.g., the appearance of a field) and underlying values (i.e., the values that these symbols convey) of their local culture (Burton 2004; Burton et al. 2021).

Many studies referring to the GF concept draw on Bourdieusian theory (see Burton et al. 2021; Burton and Paragahawewa 2011; Sutherland and Darnhofer 2012; Sutherland 2013; Westerink et al. 2021) and its three components of habitus, field and capital (Bourdieu 1998; Burton et al. 2021). Bourdieu (1990) conceptualises ‘field’ as an essential social domain characterised by competition among agents for power and valued resources. These structured arenas of struggle can be observed in diverse areas, including economics, politics, law and education (Pronti et al. 2025). Habitus is Bourdieu’s term for the collection of ingrained habits, perceptions, and beliefs that individuals develop throughout their lives. This internal framework is formed by our social experiences and, in turn, shapes the way we naturally behave and interact in different social environments (Costa and Murphy 2015). Likewise, Bourdieu conceptualises multiple forms of capital—economic, cultural, social, symbolic—which function as strategic resources. Agents deploy these resources to accumulate both material advantages and symbolic profits, such as dominance, prestige, or social legitimacy (Bourdieu 1990).

The key component of Bourdieu’s theory that the GF concept refers to is symbolic capital. This form of capital consists of the shared symbols, habits, and unconscious practices that a community recognises as valuable (Bourdieu 1990). The identity of a GF is then built through actions that carry such symbolic meaning. A classic example is what Burton (2004) called ‘hedgerow farming’. This describes how farmers often prioritise making their most visible land and livestock look impeccable. A well-kept field by the road is more than just good cultivation; it is a powerful non-verbal statement to the community that

the farmer is skilled, diligent and trustworthy. This focus on appearance is thus an investment in symbolic capital (Burton et al. 2008). Farmers invest in symbolic capital to achieve social status such as acceptance by others and belonging to the farming community. This can substantially influence the adoption, or non-adoption, of new agricultural practices, techniques or technologies, depending on how the community perceives them (Pronti et al. 2025).

Further, cultural capital is of importance for the GF concept, comprising skills, knowledge and qualifications (Bourdieu 1986) that can be gained through upbringing, education and experience (Burton 2004; Westerink et al. 2021). In the farming context, cultural capital refers to being identified as a GF by the relevant community. This reputation is built on farming ability and strengthened by the production of the symbols that can be seen or are displayed in the field (Sutherland and Burton 2011). These symbols may include little erosion (Lavoie and Wardropper 2021) or 'tidy' fields (Burton et al. 2021). In short, the concept posits that farmers aim to be recognised as a GF to gain (cultural and symbolic) capital. This aspiration for a good reputation influences behaviour and farming strategies (Burton et al. 2021).

In fact, the transformation of a farming system requires societal acceptance of a diversity of practices (Lähdesmäki et al. 2019). It can therefore take generations to change symbols and norms, especially if changes are introduced by policy or market demands (Haggerty et al. 2009) and do not come from within the community. A change in norms may also not be universal: Agri-environmental policy, subsidies, or direct marketing options have been shown to lead to a diversification of GF symbols rather than their replacement (Sutherland and Darnhofer 2012; Huttunen and Peltomaa 2016). This diversification results in different groups of farmers sharing different GF norms and referring to different symbols. For example, farmers using conservation agriculture have been found to hold different core GF concepts than farmers using conventional tillage (Topp et al. 2024).

A host of studies describe GF symbols and norms in various settings. One of the earliest studies by Burton (2004) describes the prevailing GF symbols of high crop yields, neat and clean landscapes, a tidy farm and the quality of crop and livestock. GF characteristics such as taking good care of the land, soil, and livestock, having good financial management, and behaving responsibly in relation to society and the environment, being social, happy, and working hard are, for example, mentioned by Westerink et al. (2021) about farmers in the Netherlands. Leitschuh et al. (2022) find that according to farmers in the US, a GF cares about their future generation, takes good care of the land, is efficient and profit oriented. Sutherland and Darnhofer (2012) found features like tidiness, timeliness of task completion, 'doing the job right', hard work, clean fields, livestock in good condition, preservation of soil fertility, making good use of resources, making a profit and being progressive related to GF in England.

Studies covering multiple regions are scarce, but a recent study including several Mediterranean countries (Topp et al. 2024) shows that GF norms largely align across these climatically

similar regions. Across the countries investigated, farmers value productivity (high yields, good crop productivity), farmer characteristics such as possessing experience and knowledge, being observant, being open to 'new practices, technologies and innovations', having the willingness to learn, and being economically profitable, and farm- and soil management practices such as using mineral fertilisers and tillage (Topp et al. 2024). To the best of our knowledge, no study to date investigates the differences and nuances in farmers' norms across different climatic zones.

Most of the existing research on GF symbols does not explicitly use the phrase 'good farmer' in the data collection process (Sutherland 2021). As we outline below, we asked our interviewees directly to identify and describe a GF in their locale and describe the visible symbolic aspects that come to mind in this respect. Our rationale was that farmers can naturally relate to the idea of a 'good farmer' or a 'role model,' while talking about norms or symbols in an abstract sense can be challenging (Burton et al. 2021; Sutherland 2021).

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: First, we describe our methodological approach and the selection of regions (chapter 2). Next, we present the results (chapter 3) and discuss them in the context of sustainable soil management (chapter 4). Finally, we provide key findings and recommendations for policy implementation and further research (chapter 5).

2 | Data and Methods

To elicit farmers' GF norms, we analysed 101 semi-structured interviews with farm decision makers in four case study regions in Austria, Switzerland, Spain, and Sweden in the spring and summer of 2023. Each case study region is part of a different major environmental zone (Metzger et al. 2012), resulting in different prevailing farming systems.

2.1 | The Case Study Regions

Our case study regions comprise the *Weinviertel* in the north-east of Austria, *Guadalajara* in central Spain, the *Plain Areas of Svealand* in Eastern Sweden, and the *Central Plateau* that stretches across Switzerland. Figure 1 shows the NUTS-2 regions (NUTS: Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics; NUTS-2: 2nd largest NUTS units) of Europe where the case study regions are located. The corresponding NUTS-2 regions are AT12 in Austria, CH02 in Switzerland, ES42 in Spain, and SE12 in Sweden.

Appendix A provides regional statistical information on farm structure and farmer demographics, showing how farm sizes, types, and structure as well as tillage practice use and participation in agri-environment-climate measures (AECM) vary across contexts (Note that where case study regions spanned more (e.g., Switzerland) or less (e.g., Austria) than one entire NUTS-2 region, we describe data for the NUTS-2 region where most interviews were done). Farms are largest in the Swedish case study region and smallest in Switzerland, where livestock prevails. Organic farms are more common in Austria and Sweden and

FIGURE 1 | Location of the case study regions at NUTS-2 level. Created using packages *eurostat* (Lahti et al. 2017, 2023) and *ggplot2* (Wickham 2016) in R (R Core Team 2024). *Data source*: Eurostat n.d.

reduced tillage in Austria and Switzerland. AECM participation is very high in both Austria and Sweden, payments are highest in Austria. Austria also has the lowest share of non-family labour but more female farmers than the other regions; there are particularly few female farmers in Switzerland.

2.1.1 | Austria—Weinviertel

The Austrian case study region—the Weinviertel, located in Lower Austria and northeast of Vienna—is characterised by a warm continental climate with an average annual temperature of 10°C–12°C and approximately 500 mm of yearly precipitation (GeoSphere Austria n.d.). Climate change is expected to impact the region and already has led to increased weather extremes, including summer droughts, high temperatures, and heavy rainfall events, which pose erosion risks in hilly areas. Some farmers are already adapting their practices, supported by AECM of the Austrian common agricultural policy (CAP) that promote reduced tillage and cover cropping. The participation in such schemes is generally very high in Austria, compared to other EU countries (Zimmermann and Britz 2016). Nevertheless, many farmers expressed dissatisfaction with agricultural policy during our interviews, perceiving the associated regulations as limiting. At the time of the interviews, the

weather was cooler and wetter than typically in recent years during that period.

2.1.2 | Switzerland—Swiss Central Plateau

The Swiss Central Plateau spans from southwest to northeast Switzerland and has the highest proportion of agricultural and arable land in the country (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft 2021). The region's climate is continental and temperate (Metzger et al. 2012). The annual mean temperatures vary between 8°C and 12°C (Bundesamt Für Meteorologie Und Klimatologie MeteoSchweiz n.d.), and the annual precipitation ranges from 800 to 1400 mm (National Centre for Climate Services 2021). Climate change presents both challenges (e.g., more droughts and heavy rainfall) and opportunities (e.g., higher yields due to increased temperatures (Henne et al. 2017)). Swiss agricultural policy, similar to the EU's CAP, includes the proof of ecological performance, a cross-compliance mechanism linking payments to minimum ecological standards, which supports the ecological performance of the sector (Huber et al. 2024). During the Interviews some farmers expressed frustration towards certain measures related to receiving subsidies (see Bütikofer 2023). The Interviews were conducted during a cooler-than-usual season.

2.1.3 | Spain—Guadalajara

The Spanish region Guadalajara, located northeast of Madrid, has an average annual temperature of 13°C and an average annual precipitation of 429 mm. The summers in Guadalajara are long, dry and hot with little rainfall (Muñoz et al. 1989). Climate change is causing higher temperatures and less precipitation in the region. Similar to interviewees in Austria and Switzerland, many interviewed farmers expressed considerable frustration with policy and the bureaucracy associated with CAP payments, and a sense of alienation from society (see also Lunar-Koch 2024). The 2 years prior to the interview time were characterised by below-average rainfall in the case study region, and the months directly before the interviews were particularly dry and warm. Interviewees therefore reported an increase in drought-related problems and resulting economic concerns. Some interviewees were nevertheless sceptical towards the existence of (anthropogenic) climate change and attributed the weather changes to other factors.

2.1.4 | Sweden—Plain Areas of Svealand

The Swedish case study region, located north of Stockholm, has a cool and temperate climate with a short growing season

(Metzger et al. 2012), and an average annual temperature of 6°C–7°C and 400–600 mm yearly precipitation (SMHI n.d.). The region has some of the most fertile soils in Sweden. Short growing seasons with early summer droughts are a frequent challenge for agriculture. Like in Austria and Switzerland, environmental issues in agriculture are high upon the political agenda in Sweden. Like in the other regions, the Swedish interviewees expressed discontent with policy and regulations, especially in dairy systems and in relation to international competitiveness. During the interview period drought was also a concern. The interview partners talked about the risk for a new season as dry as in 2018.

2.2 | Data Collection and Analysis

Our target group for the interviews was the main decision makers of farms that had arable land in the case study regions. We aimed to maximise the diversity of farm types and farmer characteristics. The farms thus differed in size, organic/conventional management, tillage methods and farm type; the interviewees were either owner-managers or managers and differed in gender and age. Table 1 provides an overview of interviewees' demographic information and structural differences between farms by case study region.

TABLE 1 | Interviewees' demographic and farm structural information by case study region.

	Full sample	Austria	Switzerland	Spain	Sweden
Total (<i>N</i>)	102	27	24	20	31
Gender (<i>N</i> female)	7	2	1	2	2
Gender (<i>N</i> male)	95	25	23	18	29
Age (mean, min-max)	49 (21–72)	46 (21–65)	48 (31–64)	52 (35–63)	50 (29–72)
Level of formal agricultural education (<i>N</i> none)	11	2	2	0	7
Level of formal agricultural education (<i>N</i> lower)	27	4	6	7	10
Level of formal agricultural education (<i>N</i> higher)	40	13	12	8	7
Level of formal agricultural education (<i>N</i> university)	24	8	4	5	7
Cropland (ha) (mean median)	258 150	324 99	21 20	337 338	327 201
Farm type (<i>N</i> farm has livestock)	44	5	22	2	15
Organic (<i>N</i> yes)	36	11	12	0	13
Organic (<i>N</i> no)	60	16	9	19	16
Organic (<i>N</i> partly/in conversion)	6	0	3	1	2
<i>N</i> full-time farming	61	14	5	20	22
<i>N</i> part time farming	22	3	10	0	9
<i>N</i> no answer for full/part time farming	19	10	9	0	0
Crop rotation (mean <i>N</i> of crops)	6.0	7.5	5.9	5.6	5.1

In Austria, Switzerland, and Sweden we purposefully recruited interview partners via agricultural extension agencies and associations, experts, advisors, and scientists, complemented by online searches, a call for participation in agricultural newspapers, personal networks and snowballing. Interviews typically took place on the interviewees' farms. In Spain, we approached most interviewees at a regional farmers' association office and asked them to participate directly on-site. Additional participants were identified by snowballing and interviewed on-farm.

We aimed to interview 20–30 farmers per region, covering a diversity of structural aspects and farmer demographics. We conducted 112 interviews in total, but 11 participants had difficulties answering the questions on the GF or did not provide answers for analysis, mostly because they did not want to 'judge' other farmers. In a few cases, the interviewed decision makers were two people, and in one case both interviewees provided demographic information. Our results are hence based on 101 interviews, and we show demographic data for 102 individuals. Due to the qualitative nature of our study, the results are not representative of the farmers in the case study regions.

The interviews comprised three sections: (1) several open-ended questions related to the structure of the farm and the practiced soil management; (2) a Q-methodological study on soil management that is analysed and presented in a separate contribution (not yet published), and (3) a series of open-ended questions on participants' perceptions of characteristics and symbols of a GF as outlined in Figure 2. The present contribution analyses the answers from part (3) only. At the end of the interview, we asked participants to fill out a paper-based questionnaire that included several statements about farming systems, practices, and symbols of a GF on a five step Likert scale. The interview guideline and questionnaire (Leonhardt, Braitto, Bütikofer, et al. 2025) and anonymised data (Leonhardt, Braitto, Graversgaard, et al. 2025) are available in a repository.

We conducted all interviews in person in local languages with one or two researchers present during each interview. We recorded all interviews. In Austria, Spain and Switzerland we transcribed all recordings. For the Swedish interviews we created field notes and transcribed only selected interview sections due to time limitations. Since the Interviews were conducted in local languages, the interview transcripts and notes were analysed by different researchers and later in the process the codes and quotes were translated to compare between case study results.

FIGURE 2 | Questions about the GF concept as provided in the interview guideline.

2.3 | Data Analysis

We used qualitative content analysis (Mayring 2022) with an inductive coding strategy to analyse the sections of the transcripts and field notes relating to a GF. Answers about bad farmers were only used to validate results, as they do not necessarily imply that the *opposite* characteristics and symbols of a bad farmer apply to a GF. The guiding questions for the analysis were 'How do interviewees characterise a GF?' and 'Which symbols do farmers use to identify a GF?' Symbols were defined as aspects that are visible to others. We first analysed the transcripts/notes from each case study region individually, creating a list of preliminary codes for GF characteristics and symbols, respectively. We supported the codes with quotes. We then harmonised the preliminary codes across case study regions and languages and re-analysed the transcripts using the harmonised codes. When needed, we added new codes and revised the set of codes in an iterative process. The full set of codes is provided in the Appendix A.

We analysed the relevant answers to the questionnaire using descriptive statistics and visualisations. We created boxplots to visualise differences in responses across the case study regions using the package ggplot2 (Wickham 2016) in R (R Core Team 2024). We note that these results are based only on the rather small and purposefully non-representative (in a statistical sense) sample of interview partners and should therefore be interpreted with caution.

3 | Results

This chapter summarises first the good farming norms described by the interviewed farmers in terms of characteristics and symbols, followed by the results of the questionnaire. IDs such as 'AT12' refer to interviewees and their region. Bold text highlights codes; these are also summarised in Tables 2 and 3 in Section 3.2; Appendix B provides code definitions. The sequence of the narrative descriptions by case study reflects the respective relative importance of the GF characteristics and symbols, beginning with the most prevalent topics.

3.1 | Good Farmer Norms: Characteristics and Symbols

3.1.1 | Austria

For the Austrian interviewees, the main characteristics of a GF were to be open-minded towards new methods and technology, to be curious and open to learn, and thus willing to improve farming techniques. These aspects are summarised under the theme of being open minded. Farmers also described a certain level of self-reflection and humbleness as good: 'A good farmer is probably one who learns from their mistakes, corrects them, improves upon them... so that they do things better in the future and keep learning continuously' (AT01). Other important themes were being attentive to details, having good timing, for example, for harvesting, sowing, or tillage, and being adaptive to local conditions. Being economically strategic and being a good businessperson, who, for example, thinks and works efficiently,

were further important features of a GF for the Austrian interviewees: '[A good farmer] considers the long-term profitability of his operation in his decisions' (AT30). Relatedly, long-term thinking in terms of considering future generations and farm successors as well as considering environmental sustainability when managing the farm were seen as characteristics of a GF. In terms of interaction with the farming community, respecting and collaborating with other farmers and society was a characteristic expected from a GF. This, again, requires a certain level of openness: 'openness to dialogue, listening, trying out new things, not being stubborn' (AT21). Finally, a few farmers mentioned that a GF would also enjoy their work.

Symbols of good farming that the Austrian participants mentioned include a healthy soil and visible strategies that are beneficial for the soil: 'a good farmer is someone who focuses on crop rotation, who also tries to build up the soil, humus-wise, with cover crops, who... doesn't drive around in the field in any weather to destroy soil structure.' (AT23). A good harvest and good yields were also important, tied to healthy and uniform crops: 'you can tell whether someone has good crops, so good yields are generated' (AT27). Some respondents further mentioned tidy and neat fields and farms, including 'acceptable' (AT02) fields with few weeds when asked for visible symbols of a GF.

3.1.2 | Switzerland

In the Swiss case study region, many interviewees considered a GF as someone who is open minded. This implies being open to change and innovation, experimenting, trying new methods and learning from results. Similarly, being self-reflective and curious was seen as good: 'Someone who thinks a little about how they do their work and who is perhaps also a little self-critical... Someone who can reflect, who can say "yes, I didn't do that well, someone else can do it better"' (CH06). Good timing and 'having a feeling for agriculture' (CH12) was also important but requires sufficient time, as CH01 explained: 'you have to make sure that farmers can make a living from [farming]... So that they have time to be good farmers.' Hence, a GF must also be a good businessperson who knows the market and acts accordingly. At the same time, a GF prioritises environmental sustainability and takes care of resources including land, animals, biodiversity and the soil, 'simply taking nature into account. We have to work with it, if we destroy it, then we... no longer exist.' (CH08). Further, according to some interviewees, a GF is attentive, willing to learn and accurate, for example, by paying attention to how crops look and acting accordingly. They collaborate with others, act in an economically strategic way and produce (healthy) food for society. Finally, a few Swiss interviewees mentioned that a GF should enjoy working in agriculture, that is, do their work 'with joy and with love' (CH10).

Visible symbols of good farming that were mentioned by Swiss interviewees often focus on the use of cover crops, crop rotations, and other soil-preserving management practices. These reflect that a farmer has the necessary knowledge about 'micro-nutrient cycles, cycles of soil life, understanding these and then managing them in such a way that they are preserved' (CH11). Next, a number of farmers mentioned the keeping of livestock in

general or well-kept livestock in particular as a symbol of good farming. A tidy farm and fields or healthy crops and few weeds were described as important by some farmers. One farmer referred to good machinery and knowing how to use it as another visible symbol.

3.1.3 | Spain

For many of the interviewees from the Spanish case study region being a good businessperson, that is, working efficiently and understanding the market to make a (good) living, as well as being economically strategic and running a viable business, were very important characteristics of a GF: 'What makes a good farmer? Well, the most important thing is that he works profitably. In the end, money is the most important thing' (ES07). Others, like ES19, considered economics important but not paramount: 'Having only money in mind also makes you blind. You have to take care of money and know how to manage it well, but it's not everything'. Related characteristics that also serve the farm business were open mindedness and openness to innovations or new methods and adaptiveness to local conditions and change. This was sometimes also linked to economic viability. Thinking about the future and future generations was important, too, as was enjoying the work in agriculture which, for example, ES14 relates to doing the work well: 'I am a farmer because I like it. And I want to do it well. If I do something, I do it well or else I can quit'. Some Spanish farmers mentioned attentiveness and accuracy or good timing, and a few considered the production of food or other characteristics as important.

As visible symbols of good farming, good machinery, not necessarily big or new machines, but ones that are 'doing a good job', were mentioned by many of the Spanish interviewees. Similarly, frequently mentioned were soil-preserving management practices. Furthermore, neat and tidy fields and farms and, correspondingly, little weeds on the fields were symbols of good farming: 'If you have the fields in order. That's always a good sign. Then you have fewer weeds' (ES22). Several interviewees considered good yields as important visible symbols, and individual farmers also mentioned (well-kept) livestock or healthy, uniform crops.

3.1.4 | Sweden

Many of the Swedish interviewees expressed that a GF is a good businessperson, for example, knows when to buy or sell, or is good at investing. SE27 stated that 'instead of saying farmers, I would say agricultural entrepreneurs... I think that those who always manage to develop and sustain a good economy over time [are good farmers], they can do good investments.' Further, good timing, that is 'being able to do the right things at the right time' (SE33), was considered an important characteristic that is based on the farmer's experiential knowledge and the ability to consider several factors (weather, pests, weeds) at the same time. This implies that being attentive and accurate was also seen as important for being a GF. Being open-minded, for example, towards new methods, new technology, or other farmers and colleagues is another characteristic that was mentioned frequently. Several farmers considered adaptiveness to local conditions

important, others referred to environmental sustainability, which includes considering the environment, taking care of the soil and working with nature. In terms of an attitude towards work, several of the Swedish interviewees highlighted being hard-working (e.g., working a lot, finding good solutions to problems, being very dedicated to farming in general, and ‘getting the job done’) as an important characteristic, next to being economically strategic or self-reflective and humble. For example, a GF was described as someone who does ‘not always believe that what [they] do is best’ (SE22). Other aspects, for example, collaborating with other farmers or considering future generations, were mentioned by few interviewees.

As visible symbols of good farming, several interviewees mentioned tidy fields and a tidy, orderly, and well-kept farm (e.g., a clean and safe environment) as important: ‘when you plough or whatever you do. It should be nice and tidy’ (SE22). Some tolerated a certain level of weeds or acknowledged that this depends

on the natural conditions. Healthy crops (dependent on the context, such as weather conditions) as a foundation of a good yields were also mentioned by many interviewees, as was the use of soil-preserving management practices. SE16 specified that ‘well-managed farms and fields can indicate a good farmer, but not always so. Well-kept animals indicate a good farmer’ (SE16), a notion that was shared by several others too. Some interviewees also mentioned the presence of livestock as a symbol of a GF, or few weeds in the fields.

3.2 | Comparison Between Case Study Regions

Tables 2 and 3 summarise the codes and their prevalence for GF characteristics and symbols from the qualitative analysis. It is important to note that frequencies are always relative to the available material per case study region (i.e., number of interviews and extent of answers given by interviewees). One dot

TABLE 2 | Code summary describing characteristics of a GF (guiding question for analysis: How do interviewees characterise a GF?) and their importance relative to the case study region sample.

Characteristics	Austria	Switzerland	Spain	Sweden
Adaptive to local conditions
Attentive and accurate
Considering future generations
Economically strategic
Enjoying the work
Good businessperson
Good timing
Hard-working
Open minded (to change, innovation, new methods, curious...)
Producing food
Reflective (self-reflection and humbleness)
Respectful and collaborating with other farmers
Environmentally sustainable and working with nature

TABLE 3 | Code summary describing symbols of a GF (guiding question for analysis: Which symbols do farmers use to identify a GF?) and their importance relative to the case study region sample.

Symbols	Austria	Switzerland	Spain	Sweden
Few weeds (limited amount acceptable)
Good machinery
Good yields
Healthy and uniform crops
Keeps livestock
Neat and tidy fields and farms
Well-kept livestock
Uses soil-preserving management strategies/practices

means that the topic was mentioned only by very few individuals or not at all, two dots are also rare, which means it was mentioned by few individuals. Three dots (meaning ‘moderate’), four dots (‘frequent’) and up to five dots (‘very frequent’) imply mentioning by several individuals to almost all interviewees. The colours in table 2 and 3 are used to underline the importance for each code (light colours mentioned less; dark colours mentioned more often).

Open-mindedness and being a good businessperson appear as quite universal characteristics of a GF that were emphasised by many participants and in all regions. Similarly, being economically strategic, being adaptive, having good timing, and being attentive and accurate were mentioned by interviewees from all regions but slightly less often. There is less agreement across regions about the other mentioned characteristics. Considering future generations and farm successors was mentioned primarily by interviewees from Austria and Spain. Producing food was mentioned primarily by Swiss, while being hard-working was mentioned by Swedish farmers—contrary to enjoying the work, which was mentioned often in Spain and by individual participants in Austria and Switzerland.

Regarding the symbols used to recognise a GF, only two codes appeared in each region and thus seem universal: the use of soil-preserving management practices and neat and tidy fields and farms. Good yields were mentioned in all regions as an important symbol except Switzerland. Few weeds in the fields and good machinery were primarily mentioned by Spanish interviewees, and (well-kept) livestock were emphasised in Switzerland and Sweden.

Figure 3 depicts boxplots of the questionnaire results regarding evaluations of farming systems, practices, and symbols with regards to a GF by case study. It shows the mean (*), median (vertical line), and variation (boxplot extent, whiskers and outliers shown as dots) of participants’ responses to the respective 5-point Likert scale items. Appendix C provides the same boxplots sorted by case study. The figures show that among different farming systems, conservation and regenerative agriculture received the highest rating as signs of a GF, but slightly less in Sweden than in the other regions. Conventional farming was rated as a sign of a GF by Spanish interviewees more than by others. Among the rated farming practices, a diversified crop rotation was ranked highly by all, as were

FIGURE 3 | Results from the Questionnaire: ‘A GF applies/uses/has/...’ by case study region (1 = fully disagree; 5 = fully agree). *denotes arithmetic means; vertical lines denote the median. AT, Austria; CH, Switzerland; ES, Spain; SE, Sweden.

measures that favour biodiversity. Cover crops and reduced tillage were largely considered to be signs of a GF by Austrian and Swiss farmers, and less so by Spanish and Swedish farmers. Spanish farmers ranked ploughing higher than all others. Most variation between case studies seems to exist regarding symbols of a GF. Interviewees from the Swedish and Spanish case study regions ranked the ‘classic’ GF symbols of high yields, minimal weeds, and tidy fields as more important than participants from the Austrian and Swiss regions. To a smaller extent, this is also true for straight lines on the fields. Only Spanish farmers considered big machines somewhat of a GF symbol.

4 | Discussion

4.1 | Characteristics and Symbols of a Good Farmer in the Four Regions

In summary, our analysis of good farmer norms in four different European regions with different pedoclimatic and cultural contexts shows the following results. When asked openly about what makes a GF according to their personal thoughts, interviewees from all regions talked about open-mindedness, adaptiveness, attentiveness, and having good timing, as well as about being a good businessperson and being economically strategic. Hence, norms of good farming refer to both practical skills ‘in the field’ as well as business skills, confirming previous findings by, for example, Topp et al. (2024). A long-term orientation towards environmental sustainability or future generations was also mentioned frequently (though not in all regions), demonstrating that stewardship norms that extend to the environment are relatively widespread (see, e.g., Leitschuh et al. 2022; Firnhaber et al. 2024; Saunders 2016). When asked about visible symbols, the most-mentioned aspects were soil-preserving management practices, neat and tidy fields and farms, and good yields, providing a mix of ‘classic’ production- and appearance-oriented, and more conservation-focused norms. The questionnaire results confirm that the former symbols of a GF are still widespread, but farming systems and practices that focus on soil conservation (e.g., regenerative agriculture, cover crops) or biodiversity are indeed more strongly associated with a GF than conventional farming (including ploughing) systems and practices—or organic farming. This confirms studies which show that currently, both the classic production-oriented and the conservation-focused norms (especially those referring to soil conservation) exist alongside (Westerink et al. 2021; Leitschuh et al. 2022), perhaps indicating that a slow shift is taking place (Firnhaber et al. 2024).

Comparing the results across case study regions, we find the commonalities described above, but also many differences. For example, the general attitude of a GF towards farm work was described differently in the regions as either an enjoyment of work (Spain, Switzerland) or as hard work (Sweden), suggesting different prevailing work ethics and cultures. Swiss and Austrian farmers mention collaboration with other farmers as another important characteristic, perhaps because many of the interviewees from these countries were members of associations and groups that foster conservation agriculture, and collaboration in, for example, machine syndicates is

rather common. Some further differences that we identify are likely related to pedoclimatic differences. Practices such as cover cropping, reduced tillage, and conservation agriculture are challenging to implement in a wet and cold climate with a short growing season (Heller et al. 2024). This may be the reason why, compared to all others, the Swedish interviewees did not consider these practices as important signs of a GF. Surprisingly, however, it was the Spanish farmers who conversely considered ploughing a sign of a GF, more than all others. This may be related to symbols such as big machines, high yields, straight lines, tidy fields, or minimal weeds that were also ranked highest by the Spanish interviewees (and partly also by Swedish interviewees) and suggest that production-focused, hence often called ‘productivist’, norms (Burton and Wilson 2006; Braitto et al. 2020; Bartkowski et al. 2022) prevail among these farmers more so than among their colleagues in Austria and Switzerland.

In addition, the Spanish interviewees tended to place greater emphasis on a GF being a good businessperson than others. All Spanish interviewees work full-time on their farm, which is not the situation in the other regions (see Table 1) and might explain these differences. This shows that a household’s farming strategy—whether it involves specialising in certain crops, focusing on market sales, or committing to full-time farming—can influence and (re)shape the characterisation of a GF and its associated symbolic capital. Household strategies are the medium to long-term plans of farming and thus embody the household’s values (Larcher et al. 2019). Therefore, understanding the types of strategies farmers employ (e.g., specialisation, stable reproduction, disengagement; see Larcher et al. 2019) is essential for understanding their norms. This also reflects in other GF symbols we identified, well-kept livestock and the keeping of livestock in general. These symbols were only mentioned in livestock-rich regions, reflecting the prevalence of this farming strategy.

This existence of some substantial similarities across a diverse sample spanning several regions aligns with the findings of the (to the best of our knowledge) only other multi-regional GF study by Topp et al. (2024). This study finds that GF norms are linked to ‘being open to new practices’, ‘having the willingness to learn’, ‘obtaining high yields and productivity’, ‘being economically profitable’, ‘being observant’ and ‘having right timing’ across several climatically similar regions (Topp et al. 2024). The authors argued that the differences they identified across regions are due to regional and household strategy reasons that underly different norms (Topp et al. 2024). Our results confirm this, but add that environmental conditions, which differed across our study regions, do seem to have an influence on GF norms too.

Several of our interviewees mentioned that GF symbols are context specific, confirming the findings of other studies (Burton 2004). Interviewees also explained that they would need to know a farmer and their ways for several years before they could ‘judge’ whether a farmer is a GF or not. In the Swedish region, there was also an understanding that all farmers have good and bad years, and that the weather greatly influences production, also confirming results from the literature (Westerink et al. 2021).

4.2 | The Good Farmer and Soil Management Practices

The GF norms we identify can have both enabling and inhibiting effects on farmers' use of climate-smart soil management practices such as cover cropping or reduced tillage. Characteristics such as openness to change and a long-term orientation have been shown to increase the likelihood of the uptake of sustainable or biodiversity-friendly farming practices (Dessart et al. 2019; Klebl et al. 2024). They therefore likely benefit the uptake of climate-smart management practices, as they may encourage farmers to try new practices, learn new skills and focus on practices with long-term benefits. These norms related to openness also give farmers room to experiment with and learn new practices—which in the beginning might produce symbols of 'bad' farming (e.g., a high level of weeds, failed crops or low yields)—if they prevail in the local community (Lavoie and Wardropper 2021). The farmers in this study generally also believed that a GF is considerate of the soil and the environment, and that the use of extensive and soil preserving practices, diversified crop rotations and healthy soils convey farming ability to an observer. This fits well within sustainable soil management practices and is therefore likely to enable their uptake, as demonstrated by a host of literature that finds that pro-environmental attitudes, 'post-productivist' self-identities, or stewardship motives support the use of environmentally sustainable farming practices (Carlisle 2016; Dessart et al. 2019; Klebl et al. 2024; Prokopy et al. 2019). Farmers often take decisions based on deeply held habitus, for example, subsistence habitus (Vogel and Wiesinger 2003). Those who think in terms of multiple generations and have an ingrained ecological mindset tend to develop a unique identity, which is reflected in specific characteristics and symbols associated with GF.

Some of the symbols of a GF we identify could inhibit the use of climate-smart soil management practices, for example tidy fields and good yields. These 'classic' symbols of a GF (Burton et al. 2021) are linked to a 'productivist' mindset (Burton and Wilson 2006; Braitto et al. 2020; Bartkowski et al. 2022), which is negatively associated with the uptake of sustainable agricultural practices (Klebl et al. 2024). It is, however, important to remember that the norms linked to a GF describe what farmers strive to be, not what they actually do and implement. The meaning of 'tidy' can also evolve over time to allow for, for example, reduced tillage (Firnhaber et al. 2024). The norms related to good timing and attentiveness could also have an ambiguous or inhibiting effect: These standards may be difficult for farmers to live up to during the time it takes to learn how to use new practices (Burton et al. 2021), as it can take several seasons to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge.

The norms related to farm economics can be both inhibiting or enabling for the use of climate-smart soil management practices. On the one hand, it can be economically beneficial to use sustainable soil management practices due to, for example, increased efficiency, lower input use, or subsidies (Cusworth 2020; Westerink et al. 2021). On the other hand, there is a risk of failing when trying a new practice. If a farmer's only goal is to 'survive' (as mentioned by several of the Spanish farmers), it can be very difficult to find economic room for manoeuvre. For farmers who work full-time, and whose livelihood depends on a successful harvest, the stakes of failure are even higher. Then again, local conditions

may also 'force' farmers to change in order to make a living, if practices can mitigate the effects of extreme weather events.

4.3 | The Good Farmer in Policy Making

There are two main policy recommendations that can be drawn from this study and the conceptual lens of the GF. First, the commonalities in the norms that we identify across regions can serve as possible anchor points for agri-environmental policy. Especially those norms that likely enable a desired change in farming practices could be leveraged and supported by providing practical information and advice or economic support to farmers. This could be done by providing tailored information that addresses norms ('information framing', see also Braitto et al. 2020), by subsidies that economically enable the use of sustainable soil management practices that may be of interest to those who are open to change, or by offering risk-management instruments that mitigate economic risks of such changes. However, the differences in prevailing norms that we identify also present challenges for one-size-fits-all policy solutions, such that regional specifications of such policies may be necessary. Moreover, communication strategies to redefine the symbols of good agricultural practices, for example, tidy fields, may be relevant as well.

Second, the GF concept demonstrates, as much of the existing literature, the importance of norms, which are closely related to the communities that farmers are embedded in (e.g., Dessart et al. 2019; Klebl et al. 2024; Ranjan et al. 2019). Any practice that is to be used by farmers must not only fit local conditions and be economically feasible, but it must also be supported by the norms of a community that farmers can refer to and feel accepted by, be it the local farming community or an online or offline network. Such communities allow farmers to share knowledge, compare different techniques and gain cultural and/or social capital (Ranjan et al. 2019; Klebl et al. 2024). Their support is particularly crucial if farmers try practices that are not 'accepted' in their local farming community, and they therefore risk to be seen as 'bad' farmers, for example, during risky years with potentially bad crops and 'messy' fields (Lavoie and Wardropper 2021; Westerink et al. 2021). Communities that share and support norms, which are supportive of conservation farming or other climate-smart soil management strategies, should therefore be created and fostered.

4.4 | Limitations and Methodological Considerations

Our study has some limitations that also provide methodological insights. First, the data analysed in this study were collected at the end of longer interviews and some interviewees gave only brief answers. Others mentioned that the first part of the interview already made them think about relevant themes, especially regarding soil management, which helped them answer the GF questions. However, this might have influenced our results with the GF answers relating more to good soil management, due to the first part of the interview focusing on this topic. As a result, the depth of the answers to the GF questions varied greatly. Previous studies regarding the GF concept are mostly based on in-depth interviews (Burton et al. 2021) that generate more detailed data. Our results are

hence not fully comparable to other studies. Moreover, since our analysed texts were sometimes just short paragraphs, we could not analyse the individual backgrounds or cultural aspects that relate to the provided answers.

Second, we directly used the phrase ‘good farmer’ in the interviews, which eased interpretation and supported the analysis. However, as the word ‘good’ has a normative connotation and some farmers did not wish to ‘judge’ others, the GF questions were sometimes met with skepticism. Sutherland (2021) suggests that it might be easier for interviewees to talk about a ‘good’ farmer rather than a ‘bad’ farmer for the same reasons. In our study, some farmers, especially in Spain, indeed found it easier to describe a ‘bad’ farmer rather than a ‘good’ one—suggesting language-specific nuances in meaning (see also below). Sutherland (2021) also notes that only a few researchers have asked farmers to describe what characterises this opposite of a GF, that is, a bad farmer. Our findings indicate that it is a possible way to go, as it sometimes produced more responses from interviewees than otherwise. It should be noted that some symbols, for example, a bad crop, do not necessarily imply a bad farmer, as other factors like adverse weather conditions may be the underlying cause (Westerink et al. 2021). Accordingly, farmers will not automatically identify a colleague who fails to produce symbols of good farming as a bad farmer (Sutherland 2021). When interviewees expressed discomfort talking about ‘good’ or ‘bad’, we also asked about role models instead, which sometimes helped interviewees.

Third, the different languages used in the study presented some challenges. Sutherland (2021) highlights that language specific differences exist in the meaning of the phrase ‘GF’, which may influence result comparability and might have caused some of the above-mentioned differences in farmers’ reactions to our questions. Further, using different languages necessitates a translation at some point during the process. This may ‘result in a loss or variation of... meaning’ (Topp et al. 2024), since language is central for interpreting qualitative data. Two strategies may be used: translating all transcripts to a common language before analysis or translating codes after analysis. We opted for the second version. While this allowed us to conduct the analysis in local languages and thus preserve all meaning at this point, it also created comparability issues in coding that could have been avoided otherwise.

Fourth, our analysis relies on a selected and non-representative sample. While this non-representativity is typical for qualitative studies (Flick 2023; Mayring 2022), where the goal is usually to include a diversity of voices and generate an in-depth understanding, it should caution the reader to draw any quantitative and definite conclusions and to place great emphasis on the results from the quantitative analysis. Like in Topp et al. (2024) we aim to provide insights into different perceptions and norms related to the GF concept. The quantitative analysis nevertheless points to an interesting avenue for future research since quantitative studies on GF norms are, to the best of our knowledge, rare.

5 | Conclusion

Our study enhances the understanding of prevailing farming norms related to the GF concept in four European regions. We find

commonalities across regions: a GF is viewed as open-minded, attentive, with good timing, and economically strategic or a good businessperson—although with different emphases in the different regions. Tidy fields with few visible weeds remain symbols of a GF, while practices that support biodiversity and diversified crop rotations are recognised too. We also observe differences between regions, for example, in the importance attributed to future generations, enjoyment of work, or environmental considerations.

Our findings have practical implications. We recommend policies, aiming to accelerate adaptation of practices to climate change, to address prevailing norms and advocate for a mix of incentives. Such policies could (i) support farmer networks that enable peer learning and experimentation with new practices; (ii) use targeted communication to reshape the meaning of visible symbols (e.g., reframing biodiversity features and less ‘tidy’ aesthetics as markers of professionalism and care); and (iii) ensure that promoted practices are economically viable, reflecting farmers’ strong orientation to business performance. Because norms are context-dependent, context-specific implementation—as implemented in the current CAP strategic plans—remains essential.

As our study is based on a qualitative design, further research could build on these and previous results to study farmers’ GF norms in a quantitative manner (e.g., using large-scale questionnaires). This could provide statistically robust insights into norms’ prevalence and allow for significance testing of differences between regions. In-depth qualitative research is also still warranted, as it can provide further insights into underlying mechanisms and driving forces of farmers’ norms. To ensure both depth and representativeness, future studies may also combine in-depth qualitative and quantitative approaches.

Author Contributions

Mariella Schreiber: formal analysis, methodology, investigation, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing. **Marion Hacek:** visualization, data curation, writing – review and editing, investigation. **Jenny Höckert:** conceptualization, investigation, funding acquisition, writing – review and editing, methodology. **Christina Lundström:** conceptualization, investigation, funding acquisition, writing – review and editing, methodology. **Mette Tiselius:** methodology, formal analysis, writing – review and editing, investigation. **Xiomara F. Quiñones-Ruiz:** methodology, writing – review and editing. **Heidi Leonhardt:** conceptualization, investigation, funding acquisition, methodology, writing – review and editing, supervision, formal analysis, project administration.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI assisted technologies in the writing process: During the preparation of this work, the authors used AI assisted transcription software to transcribe the interview audio files. AI tools

also supported the translation of transcripts. Transcripts and translations were always reviewed and edited by researchers. We used OpenAI's ChatGPT for language editing and to shorten selected paragraphs. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the text as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The anonymised quantitative data that support this study as well as the interview guidelines and questionnaire are available in a public repository, Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15730136> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15682965>. The qualitative interview data that support this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors. These data are not publicly available due to ethical and privacy concerns.

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Appendix A

Information on the structure of agriculture for the NUTS-2 regions where case study regions are (primarily) located.

NUTS-2 regions; variables	Austria	Switzerland	Spain	Sweden
Avg. LSU per ha UAA	0.59	1.46	0.38	0.42
ha UAA per farm (avg.)	31	23	38	69
% organic of total UAA	23.53	13.66	3.11	21.98
% share conservation tillage	38.39	26.29 ^b	18.89	13.45 ^a
% share no-till	2.19	3.64 ^b	3.29	1.07 ^a
% AECM: supported ha share of total UAA	95.09	No data	3.70	99.73
AECM: Euro/supported ha	2064.82	No data	601.03	1322.30
Non-family labour % of total AWU	16.82	27.52	26.36	26.79
Women farmers % of farm managers	36.7	5.3	28.1	17.2
Avg. age farm managers	52.7	54.6	64.1	61.3

Note: Unless marked otherwise, data are from Eurostat (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/data/database>) and for the latest available years at the time of writing (mostly 2016 or 2020).

Abbreviations: AECM, agri-environment-climate measure; AWU, annual work unit; LSU, livestock unit; UAA, utilised agricultural area.

^a Data for entire country; shares are higher regionally, but no data were available.

^b Data for entire country, source: <https://www.agrarbericht.ch>.

Appendix B

Code definitions.

Definitions	Characteristics of a good farmer
A GF adapts their production to the local conditions, for example, by growing certain crops that are suited for the soil, adapts production to climate change (extreme weather) or well-known weather events (e.g., plants some crops in the fall to make them resilient towards recurring pre-summer drought).	Adaptive to local conditions
A GF is attentive and accurate, for example, pays attention to how crops look and act accordingly, is accurate and pays attention to details (opposite would be one who is sloppy, careless, always behind). A GF has experience-based knowledge, for example, has learned from mistakes, from years of experience of the farm, who has a 'feeling' for the job after a lot of experience.	Attentive and accurate
A GF considers future generations, for example, when planning investments in the farm, trying to improve the soil for next generation on the farm, has a long term perspective (opposite: prioritise short-term economic gain, maximise the yields short term, leave the farm and soil less valuable for next generation).	Considering future generations
A GF has a certain level of economic strategic thinking, for example, long-term business plans. A GF prioritises economic sustainability and have good and solid economy; they have a long-term perspective on investments.	Economically strategic
A GF enjoys their work in agriculture; they have a passion for the job and a genuine interest in farming.	Enjoying the work
A GF knows how to make good deals, is a good business person, has a 'feeling'/sense' for business. They know when to sell/buy, anticipates what customers wants and makes good deals. They increase the value making on the farm, be as efficient as possible, for example, by cutting expenses, low input and worktime. A GF is making a living.	Good businessperson
A GF does the right things at the right time, for example, soil cultivate at a certain time, prioritise certain actions at the right time, and harvest at the right time. They have time to do important things.	Good timing

Definitions	Characteristics of a good farmer
A GF works hard, gets the job done no matter what time it is, prioritises the farm.	Hard-working
A GF is open to change and innovative, for example, change production system, start innovative projects on the farm and wish to develop the farm. They are experimenting and open to trying new methods, for example., minimise input use or try different kinds of crops. They are curious, for example, about different kinds of farming, new strategies, and new technology. A GF is willing to learn, for example, new methods and open towards discussions with other farmers, researchers, the public and wish to exchange knowledge with each other and learn from each other.	Open minded (to change, innovation, new methods, curious...)
A GF values producing food for society.	Producing food
A GF is self-reflective, for example, about what kind of farmer they wish to be, what strategies they use, which values they want prioritise, they have a sense of self-critique. They are humble, for example they know their knowledge is place and experience-based, humble towards other farmers.	Reflective (self-reflection & humbleness)
A GF cooperates with other farmers, for example, by sharing machines, helping each other out (e.g., sharing feed to livestock in times of drought), and pool resources. They consider neighbouring plots, for example by being careful with chemicals. They respect other farmers and their strategies and do not interfere much with other farmers.	Respectful and collaborating with other farmers
A GF prioritises sustainability. They acknowledge environmental responsibility, for example strategies that are environmentally responsible (e.g., implementing reduced tillage, building soil health, carbon farming, increasing biodiversity and less use of pesticides). A GF works with nature instead of against it, for example copy ecosystem functions in their production, create synergies, reduce tillage, and build a good soil structure.	Environmentally sustainable and working with nature
Definitions	Symbols
A GF has no or very few weeds on their fields, wants very 'clean'/'sterile' fields.	Few weeds (limited amount acceptable)
A GF has good machines and knows how to use them.	Good machinery
A GF harvests good yields through the years.	Good yields
A GF has healthy crops on their fields, for example strong, healthy crops that are resilient to the weather, are well-established. A GF has uniform crops, for example the whole field is quite uniform (no empty or 'dead' spots), the crops have similar height and colour.	Healthy and uniform crops
A GF has livestock, which is a necessary part of being a farmer. They may use manure on their fields.	Keeps livestock
A GF has neat and tidy fields and farm. Fields have straight plowing lines, limited amount of weeds (but some are okay), look well taken care of. Farm: a safe environment, things are on 'their' place/well-arranged (e.g., chemicals, tools, machinery). The garden can be well kept.	Neat and tidy fields and farms
A GF has healthy livestock, for example livestock that is well taken care of, has good weight, and looks content. A GF has 'an eye for animal welfare.	Well-kept livestock
A GF practices soil preserving strategies such as cover crops, no-till or reduced tillage, good and diversified crop rotation, focuses on biodiversity (e.g., flower strips), avoids soil compaction (e.g., drives under the right conditions) and improves soil health. A GF takes good care of their soil.	Uses soil-preserving management strategies/practices

Appendix C

Addition to Figure 3: Results from the Questionnaire: ‘A GF applies/uses/has/...’ by case study region (1 = fully disagree; 5 = fully agree). *denotes arithmetic means, vertical lines denote the median.

Austria

Switzerland

Spain

Sweden

